

PRINCIPLES OF FORMATION AND FUNCTIONING OF RUSSIAN ERGONYMS IN THE URBAN ONOMASTICS OF AZERBAIJAN

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Abstract. *The position of the ergonyms of the Russian language in the onomastic space of Azerbaijan is observed. The principles of formation and features of the use of these ergonyms are analyzed. In recent years, interest and demand for learning foreign languages has increased. This demand grows due to the integration and globalization of the modern world. The Russian language is also one of the most important among these languages. It should be noted that interest in the Russian language in Azerbaijan is growing day by day. Learners of the Russian language have many opportunities to use it in practice and benefit from the opportunities it offers. Currently, in Azerbaijan, teaching foreign languages, especially Russian, as a subject alongside the native language is brought to the forefront of intercultural communication and is widely used as an educational model. More and more bilateral agreements are being signed between these countries. A large number of meetings are held in the political arena. As it is well known, language is the most important means of communication between people. There is cooperation between Azerbaijan and Russia covering political, economic, and administrative bodies, as well as relations at the level of ordinary citizens. It is used daily in all spheres of public life: politics, economy, culture, education, tourism, healthcare, and in personal relationships between citizens.*

Key words: *onomastic space of the city, onym, onomastic system, ergonym, formation of ergonyms, ergonymy, ergonomics, onomastics.*

Language also serves as a means to maintain and expand cultural ties between the two nations. It is known that “*Onomastic units designating the names of enterprises, organizations, socio-cultural objects, camps, etc., are called ergonyms*” [Gurbanov 353 Vol. II]. Ergonyms have become an integral part of the modern linguistic space. These names reflect contemporary linguistic trends. The onomastic space of the city is enriched day by day with colorful, vivid, and original names. The development of ergonymy increases the attention paid to it by scholars, which allows for the active study of these names.

Modern cities are constantly changing and developing. The emergence of new enterprises leads to the emergence of new naming traditions. Typically, many of these traditions overlap in modern cities. However, each city has its own specific features.

Ergonyms, which occupy a special place in the onomastic system, have characteristics that distinguish them from other onyms. These names are characterized by instability, frequently changing, appearing, and disappearing. In other words, ergonyms are “*carriers of short-term background information*” [Razhina]. They are highly susceptible to external factors.

Ergonyms include names derived from units of the national language, as well as names derived from words belonging to other languages. Foreign vocabulary occupies a special place in ergonomics. “*A characteristic feature of the ergonomics of a modern city is the use of foreign*

language units and elements when creating ergonyms. Ergonyms serve as a valuable and rich source for identifying the lexical background, which is especially relevant in conditions of intensive international integration" [Habibli, 257]. Linguistic means belonging to different languages used in creating ergonyms are considered foreign. L.P. Krysin, speaking about foreign vocabulary, meant "any words and expressions that came from another language, regardless of the degree of their assimilation in the recipient language" [Krysin P. 35].

Principles of Ergonym Formation

Different principles are applied when creating ergonyms in the Russian language:

1) The principle of specialization. Many ergonyms indicate the specialization of an object in a particular field and represent thematic names:

- "Syrovarnya" (Cheese Dairy) – a restaurant offering various types of cheese and cheese products.
- "Igolochka" (Little Needle) – a shop selling items for cutting and sewing.
- "Chemodan" (Suitcase) – a shop selling a wide variety of bags and suitcases.
- "Bashmachok" (Little Shoe), "Kabluchok" (Little Heel) – such names are usually given to shoe stores.
- "Rozetka" (Socket) – a shop selling electronic goods.

Nominators conduct interesting experiments when naming pubs and breweries. The ergonym "BeerLoga" (Beer + Berloga / Bear's den) was created exactly this way.

- "Beluga" – the name of a fish restaurant, reflecting the name of the fish.
- "Doner konkretnaya pechat" (Doner Concrete Stamp) – an ergonym combining different languages and scripts. The concept of the establishment is to confirm the authenticity of something, being the only enterprise in the city that features a stamp.
- "Pivnaya Apteka" (Beer Pharmacy) – a beer bar with an atmospheric vibe. To create a pharmacy atmosphere, the staff wear white coats like pharmacists.

2) The principle of addressing (localization). An establishment is named after its location.

- For example, "Pushkin Pub". This establishment is located on A.S. Pushkin Street.
- The restaurant "Chayki" (Seagulls) is located on the Baku Boulevard, by the sea. It is well known that the sea is always associated with seagulls. Naming a seaside establishment "Chayki" is a successful step. The restaurant's location offers a magnificent view of the sea where seagulls fly.
- The cafe "Gubernator" (Governor) is located in the Philharmonic Garden. The Philharmonic Garden was founded in the 1830s on the initiative of the Baku Commandant R.R. Hoven. Built in the 1830s, the garden was formerly known as the "Governor's Garden" because it was established on the governor's initiative. The name of the cafe was chosen in accordance with the name of the garden.

3) The principle of audience targeting / addressing the consumer. Often based on this principle, children's facilities are named this way. These names are usually derived from the names of fairy-tale characters, various animals, words reflecting childhood in general, and diminutive forms of individual words:

- "Teremok.az" – an online store for children's toys. "Teremok" is a word with a diminutive meaning. It comes from the word *terem*, meaning "small terem". "Teremok" is also the title of a Russian folk tale (adapted into cartoons, operas). This ergonym can also be mentioned as a name reflecting the national-cultural background.

- “*Malyshok*” (Toddler) – this word consists of the components *mal* + *ysh* + *ok*. The name targets a specific audience.

In general, a diminutive-affectionate meaning can be added to the semantics of a specific word in the Russian language using diminutive suffixes:

- “*Khozyayushka*” (Little Housewife) – a beauty and self-care salon. The meaning is “*About a woman who manages a household well (colloquial).*” This ergonym is used as an affectionate form of the word *khozyayka* (hostess/housewife) [Ozhegov p. 2174].
- “*Bufetik*” (Little Buffet) – the name of a restaurant. It comes from the word *bufet*: “*1. A long table or counter for selling snacks and drinks, as well as the room where such sales take place, or a foyer. 2. A small snack bar. 3. A cupboard for storing dishes, table linen, snacks, drinks. II adj. bufetny, -aya, -oe*” [Ozhegov P. 133]. In Soviet times, small cafes near railway stations were called this way.
- “*Zakuska*” (Appetizer / Snack) – the name of this restaurant is formed from the Russian verb *zakusit*: “*zakusit 2 pf. 1. To eat a little (usually cold food and at an irregular time). 3. before a journey. 2. chto chem. To eat something after drinking (wine, vodka). Drank and had a mushroom snack. II impf. zakusyvat, -ayu, -aesh. if noun zakusyvanie, -ya, n. and zakuska, -i, f.*” [Ozhegov p. 504]. *Zakuska* means “*Food, a dish served before hot meals. 3. That which is eaten after drinking. Caviar for a snack. * Na zakusku (colloquial, humorous) - at the end, in conclusion. II adj. zakusochny, -aya, -oe*” [Ozhegov P. 504].
- “*Vkusnyashka*” (Yummy / Tasty Treat) – a culinary shop. In the Russian language, this word means something delicious, i.e., “*a tasty dish, food product.*” It refers to both sweets and savory delicious food.
- “*Solnyshko*” (Little Sun) – a flower shop. It comes from the word *Solntse* (Sun). The dictionary explains it as follows: “*1. see solntse. 2. Affectionately about a person (usually in address). You are my sun!*” [Ozhegov P. 1871]. We often give flowers to our loved ones on a special day. The nominator likely had this meaning of the word in mind when naming the establishment.

The main function of such ergonyms is to attract the attention of the addressee using expressive words. In these names, the emotional-expressive component dominates the word's meaning. Diminutive-affectionate suffixes serve as a means of expressiveness.

There are ergonyms that reflect national-cultural precedent phenomena, as well as names reflecting national-cultural flavor:

- Cafe “*Kalinka*” – one of the most popular names associated with the Russian people and culture.
- “*Mama nakormila*” (Mom Fed Me) – a vareniki (dumpling) cafe. This humorous name suggests that the establishment serves hearty and delicious meals.
- Restaurant “*12 Stulyev*” (12 Chairs) – an ergonym associated with the title of the famous comedy based on the novel of the same name by satirists Ilf and Petrov.
- “*Mari Vanna*” – a restaurant reminiscent of a home environment, as if you are visiting your beloved grandmother.
- “*Cheburechnaya*” – despite the fact that *cheburek* is a dish, this name was given to a teahouse. “*Cheburek (Crimean Tatar: çiberek: çiy — raw [refers to the filling], börek — patty) — originally a dish of Crimean Tatar cuisine, also included in the cuisine of Mariupol Greeks (under the name chir-chir) and North Caucasian peoples*” [<https://ru.wikipedia.org/wiki>].

In general, ergonyms that create emotionality and expressiveness always arouse particular interest among consumers. “*Trin Trava - Russkaya Izba*” (Trin-Trava - Russian Hut) is a restaurant featuring pure Russian cuisine and a rustic atmosphere.

- “*Stary Dvorik*” (Old Courtyard) – the spirit of a real old Baku courtyard reigns here, where everyone knows each other and everyone is a good friend.
- “*Yolki palki*” (Fiddlesticks / Holy Moly) – an expressive exclamation indicating surprise, regret, joy, anger, etc.

Ergonyms are also formed on the basis of general Russian vocabulary. For example: “*Shkatulka*” (Casket), “*Akvarium*” (Aquarium), “*Koleso*” (Wheel) – shop names; “*Tri Bochki*” (Three Barrels) – the name of a pub-restaurant. “*Samovar*” – we encountered several objects (teahouses, restaurants) with this name.

- “*Untsiya*” (Ounce) – this is the name of an establishment that offers high-quality, tasty, and aromatic tea, as well as coffee, sweets, and beautiful accessories. This ergonym was formed based on a technical term. An ounce is a unit of mass measurement. “The term originates from Ancient Rome; in those days, an ounce was part of the *librina* monetary unit. In the Middle Ages, it was one of the main units of weight measurement in Europe. Today, it is used as a unit of weight in the precious metals trade — the troy ounce, as well as in countries using the pound system (e.g., the USA)” [<https://www.banker.az/dict/index.php/Unsiya>].

Some ergonyms in the Russian language are associated with the concept of territory. These are ergonyms derived from topoergonyms and topoterms.

- “*Dubrovka*” – the name of a restaurant. In the Russian language, *Dubrovka* is known as a phytonym – the name of a number of perennial herbs. In addition, there is a toponym *Dubrovka* in Russia, which is known as a place name in the south-east of Moscow. Most likely, the ergonym “*Dubrovka*” was formed from the toponym.

As we can see, study of ergonyms provides a foundation for a more detailed coverage of the system of ergonyms in Azerbaijan. Ergonyms in the Russian language are very diverse in their origin and principles. Like other ergonyms, it is important to include them in linguistic analysis. This is because the primary function of these ergonyms is not only to attract attention but also to influence the choice of name.

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